

Denmark | One Health Surveillance | Avian and swine influenza

Background

- Surveillance of persons exposed to birds infected with AIV is passive and there is no dedicated surveillance for human swine influenza infections

Objectives

- Setting up an active surveillance program for persons with high-risk exposure to avian influenza (farmers, farm workers, farm residents, veterinarians and cullers with breach of personal protective equipment).
- Setting up an active surveillance program for swine influenza in veterinarians

Outcomes & Impact

- Closer collaboration between public health authorities, as well as between public health and animal health stakeholders.
- Implementation of practical setup for active surveillance of zoonotic influenza virus infections in humans
- Better insight into barriers that have prevented wider uptake in the active surveillance pilots
- Pilots provided the basis for continued work under the project UpSurvDK

Lessons learned

- One Health collaboration can be strengthened through regular and open communication, identifying common goals and differences in interests, listening to concerns and finding solutions together. The transparency and trust built as a consequence is a prerequisite to succeed in setting up similar projects.
- Finding solutions for low uptake. to increase participation in similar active surveillance projects, e.g. establishing compensation mechanisms etc.

Core messages

- Collaboration between public health and animal health stakeholders was strengthened, uncovered differences in sectoral interests and identified points for improvement.
- The Danish pilots were useful in establishing the practical setup for conducting active surveillance of zoonotic influenza virus infections in humans.
- The recommendation to self-isolate in case of a positive test result constituted a barrier in the Danish setting and negatively affected sampling uptake